

SHEAR FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF POSTBUCKLING FIBRE COMPOSITE PANELS

Noor M. Panhwar and Murray L. Scott

Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology

124 La Trobe Street, Melbourne, Victoria, 3000, Australia

ABSTRACT

An investigation of theoretical and experimental approaches to the characterisation of the performance of thin composite panels in the postbuckled state has been undertaken. Static shear and fatigue tests were performed on eight-ply, 250 mm square panels of optimised lay-up using a picture frame test rig. A servo-hydraulic testing machine was employed for loading the panels in compression-compression load control mode at a cycling frequency of 5 Hz. Tests were terminated after three million cycles. The results available from the on-going tests suggest that shear buckling ratios in excess of 7 can be employed safely in thin panels designed to operate in postbuckled states.

KEY WORDS: Carbon fibre composite, Shear buckling, Postbuckling, Fatigue

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced fibre composite structures are customarily designed to ensure that panels will not buckle under compression and shear loadings for reasons relating to aerodynamic or fatigue performance. Such a compromising philosophy is generally not imposed on metallic panels. It is common practice to allow metallic structures to employ their postbuckling strength at proof or ultimate loads. This design philosophy must be incorporated in the design of composite structures, if composites are to improve their market share. The reason for aircraft designers taking such a conservative approach whilst designing with composite materials, are associated with a general lack of understanding and experience of both the static and fatigue characteristics of postbuckling composite panels.

Although considerable research and development work has been conducted in establishing design data for composite materials, the availability of results and information is still insufficient in certain areas when compared with those for conventional isotropic materials. Much of the published research on the buckling of composite plates is theoretical in nature and is based on classical laminated plate theory. Some of the key studies undertaken on the buckling of composite plates are listed in References 1-5.

The study of the performance of composite materials under cycling loading has also been the objective of many researchers. The reviews by Salkand⁶ and Curtis and Dorey⁷ account for some of the work done on the subject of fatigue. Much of this research has been on the fatigue behaviour of unidirectional composites under tension-tension fatigue loadings. The stress-life curves of such composites are clearly defined in the literature, as the loads are mainly carried by the fibres⁸. Little attention has been given to the problem of postbuckling in general, and fatigue characteristics of postbuckling composite plates in shear in particular.

In view of this and the fact that not every composite system behaves in the same fashion under different loading conditions, the present program of research involves theoretical and experimental investigations of the fatigue and durability characteristics of thin composite panels in the postbuckling state.

2. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

2.1. Test Fixture and Panel Preparation

A newly designed picture frame test rig was employed for load application. It consisted of three basic components: straps, forks, and bolts. The 12 mm by 65 mm rectangular straps consisted of two lengths: 380 mm on one side and 230 mm on the other. A total of eight straps surrounded the four edges of each specimen. The straps were bolted to the specimens and the two forks connected the picture frame to the hydraulic grips of the testing machine via two pins.

The test panels were fabricated from T300/914C unidirectional preimpregnated, zero bleed tape. The tape was laid up by hand to form eight-ply balanced, square laminates of 380 mm edge length with a nominal thickness of 1 mm when cured. Both unidirectional and optimised quasi-isotropic laminates were cured in an autoclave using conventional vacuum bagging techniques. The manufacturer's recommended cure cycle was followed by a post cure of 4 hours at 190°C. An average fibre volume fraction of 60% (by weight) was recorded using matrix burn tests. Several panels were randomly C-scanned for any flaws occurring during manufacture. Five 12 mm holes were drilled in each side of the panel using a high speed composite drill. The 45 mm corner holes were made with a hole saw. A schematic of the assembled rig and panel orientation is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Picture frame test rig assembly and panel orientations.

2.2. Static Testing

In order to ascertain that the test rig was to be suitable for shear loading of composite panels, several preliminary tests were carried out on aluminium alloy panels and the results compared to those obtained analytically by other investigators. The static shear buckling tests were performed on unidirectional panels of 0, +45, -45, and 90 degree orientations, and quasi-isotropic panels of $[\pm 45, 90, 0]_3$ lamination to determine experimental values of buckling load, failure load, and shear modulus.

All panels were fitted with three-element strain gauges, located front and back at the centre of each panel. One quasi-isotropic panel was covered with a photoelastic coating for visual observation of the strain distribution within the panel and physical verification of the buckling mode. A linear variable differential transducer (LVDT) was employed to traverse the buckle shape and out-of-plane deflection of the quasi-isotropic panels at various nominal buckling ratios. Each panel was then clamped in position in the test rig to give a 250 mm square test area. Anti-slip strips were also placed between the panel and the rig straps to enhance load transfer through frictional contact.

A uniaxial compressive load was applied "diagonally" through the upper and lower pins using a servo-hydraulic universal testing machine in load control mode at a rate of 100 N/s. The load-deflection curve was plotted using an x-y plotter while a small computer was used to record strain data. Tests were stopped at every load interval for strain measurements. A minimum of three panels were tested in each category.

Experimental buckling loads were identified from both lateral deflections and strain gauge output reversals. Theoretical buckling loads were calculated using a simple graphical method⁹. The failure loads were determined using maximum strain theory. The buckling ratios are calculated from theoretical values of the buckling load estimated by the graphical method and the failure load. The material data presented in Table 1 were used for calculating buckling and failure loads.

Table 1. Material property values used in the present study (Source : Ciba)

Material property	Value	Material property	Value
Longitudinal modulus (MPa)	135,000	Longitudinal failure strain (%)	1.037
Transverse modulus (MPa)	8,500	Transverse failure strain (%)	0.930
Shear modulus (MPa)	5,500	Shear failure strain (%)	1.727
Long. tensile strength (MPa)	1,400	Long. comp. strength (MPa)	1,350
Trans. tensile strength (MPa)	79	Trans. comp. strength (MPa)	230
Shear strength (MPa)	95	Prepreg weight (g/sq.m)	198.0
Major Poisson's ratio	0.32	Cured ply thickness (mm)	0.125

2.3. Fatigue Testing

Only quasi-isotropic panels were tested for endurance under compression-compression load control mode. The panels were initially taken to the theoretical buckling load level before applying the desired upper limit load. This was done to avoid possible impact failure/damage by the sudden application of higher dynamic loads.

Buckling ratios of 6 to 10 were selected for load application. Various frequencies ranging from 5 Hz (for higher buckling ratios) to 8 Hz (for lower buckling ratios) were used. A minimum of three

panels were tested at each buckling ratio. Tests were terminated at the end of three million cycles or failure, whichever occurred first. The panels which did not fail after the targeted number of cycles were C-scanned for internal delamination or damaged.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Static Testing

Experimental results obtained from shear buckling tests are presented in Table 2, together with the values of the predicted buckling and failure loads of these panels. Good agreement was observed between the experimental and predicted values of the buckling loads, with scatter being approximately 10%, except for the + 45 degree panel. Correlation was poor for the failure loads of all panels. The difference between the predicted and the experimental failure loads varied between 30% and 50%.

Table 2. Experimental shear property values of T300/914C panels.

Orientation (deg)	Buckling load (kN)		Failure load (kN)		Shear Modulus (MPa)
	Predicted	Experimental	Predicted	Experimental	
0	1.82	1.60	23.75	12.12	5,000
- 45	0.70	0.70	21.60	13.10	7,140
+ 45	4.61	2.65	19.37	14.60	6,140
90	1.82	1.60	23.75	12.12	5,000
[±45,90,0] _s	2.99	2.80	62.14	44.85	8,500

A number of aspects of the theoretical and experimental work may have contributed to the variations in the preceding results, and they are as follows:

- Use of maximum tension properties in calculating theoretical failure loads
- Delay between the loading steps for strain readings
- Initial warp in some of the panels manufactured early in the program
- Asymmetric loading behaviour of the panels due to rig configuration

The last two problems listed above are confirmed by the load-strain plots of Figures 2 and 3. Some pre-straining of unidirectional panels at zero load and the unusual shear strain output of the front and back rosettes are clear indications of the sources of the problems. The failure mode for all unidirectional orientations was a crack running parallel to the fibre direction. In the case of the quasi-isotropic panels, there was no catastrophic failures, as such. Large delaminations in the middle of the central buckles and loud cracking noises were accompanied by broken fibres in the top plies in tension. This behaviour is indicated by sharp changes in the curve of Figure 3 and represents first ply failure. Similar changes in the curve can be observed in the later stages of the loading. This is presumed to be second ply failure. The subsequent breaking of fibres and plies at the strap edges caused the total failure of the panel as shown in Figure 4.

The differences between the strain output of the front and back rosettes indicate a typical characteristic of panel bending. The panel no longer experiences uniform loading at its two surfaces. This was caused by the arrangement of the rig straps and the location of the clamp holes. The transfer of shear appeared to cease after the fifth bolt on each side and induced bending and diagonal tension in the panel. This effect is represented in Figure 5.

The unsymmetrical nature of the panel loading is also visible from Figure 6 where various characteristics of a loaded panel are shown for comparison. The buckle modes, number of half-waves, and strain distribution are correlated at certain values of buckling ratios as revealed by moiré fringes and the behaviour of the photoelastic coating. Although the panel buckles in a five half-wave mode, the buckle at the centre is much larger, both in amplitude and width, when compared to the other two buckles on each side. The plot of the buckle shape showed that where the middle buckle grew 8 mm in amplitude, the other buckles were only 2.1 mm and 1.8 mm respectively.

Figure 2. Strain variation with the applied load for various unidirectional orientations.

3.2. Fatigue Testing

Some of the problems associated with the static tests carried through to the fatigue testing program as well. The local bending and diagonal tension mode of loading have left the results of these tests inconclusive. The tests are still under way as far as cycling at higher buckling ratios is concerned. From the completed tests on buckling ratios of 6, 7, and 8, only the later produced any significant failure in the test area of the panel. These panels were C-scanned after surviving the targeted number of three million cycles.

The C-scanning of one panel revealed a 20 mm wide delamination running across the length, through 70% of the panel thickness. This delamination probably initiated during first few cycles of loading when a loud cracking noise was heard. This situation corresponds to the first ply failure of these panels as discussed in the Section 3.1. No further cracking of the panel was noticed during the remainder of the cycling period.

The panels tested at lower buckling ratios revealed no significant damage in the test area of the panel. However, there were two minor areas of local delamination at the two corners of the horizontal diagonal. These areas resulted from the "squeezing" action of the smaller straps on either side of the central buckle as the panel was cycling.

Figure 3. Shear stress vs shear strain and strain vs load for a quasi-isotropic panel

Figure 4. Failed quasi-isotropic panel.

Figure 5. Effect of rig unsymmetry.

Buckling ratio 6

Buckling ratio 10

Figure 6. Comparison of moiré patterns with that observed through photoelastic coating.

4. CONCLUSION

The static and shear fatigue performance of thin quasi-isotropic, symmetric laminated, carbon fibre composite panels in the postbuckled state has been investigated. The shear buckling characteristics of unidirectional panels were also studied. From the experimental work accomplished so far, it is concluded that a shear buckling ratio of seven can be employed safely for these panels designed to operate in a postbuckled state. This ratio may be enhanced by improving the design of the present test fixture. Further testing on the cycled panels has showed no significant loss of residual strength.

Some aspects of the rig design contributed to the highly nonlinear behaviour of the panels and thus made it more difficult to predict the postbuckling performance of these panels. The final failure mode of quasi-isotropic panels in particular, can not be regarded as a typical characteristic of the type of the material and lay-up employed in this study.

In view of the overall outcome of the static shear buckling tests, with special reference to that of unidirectional panels, the results obtained while using this picture frame test rig must be used carefully. The lower values of the final failure loads of the quasi-isotropic panels were caused by creeping of the panels during intermittent stopping for strain readings. Much higher values of failure loads may be achieved if the panels are continuously loaded.

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